

Research capability using real-world data for COVID-19 vaccine effectiveness in Southeast Asia

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Abstract

Background: COVID-19 vaccine effectiveness (VE) monitoring is critical for directing control tactics. Secondary database analyses are a useful and increasingly popular research method. We evaluated the contribution of Southeast Asian (SEA) countries to the worldwide VE literature and discussed SEA hospitals' capabilities to conduct COVID-19 VE studies utilizing current databases.

Methods: The study was conducted from November 2022 to March 2023. Using the International Vaccine Access Centre's VE studies repository, we estimated SEA contribution to global COVID-19 VE publications to identify countries with limited to no publications. IQVIA's clinical research network was used to identify potential hospitals from these countries. An online, self-completion survey was adapted from the "vACCine covid-19 monitoring readinESS" protocol, to capture information on hospitals' database, VE study experience, clinical and key COVID-19 data availability. Three capability groups were defined (Good, Average, Limited). Descriptive analyses for response rate, data availability, and capability group were conducted.

Results: Asian countries contributed only 7% of the global COVID-19 VE literature, with 1.9% coming from Southeast Asia and 5.1% from the Western Pacific region. The survey included hospitals from the IQVIA research network in India, Indonesia, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. 62.5% of the eight hospitals surveyed demonstrated strong or average research capabilities.

Conclusion: This survey demonstrates the potential for real-world evidence (RWE) data generation in countries with limited RWE publications on COVID19 VE.

Keywords: Database, Secondary data analysis, COVID-19, Electronic health records, Southeast Asia, Vaccine effectiveness

Introduction

Real-world data (RWD) are defined by the European and United States regulatory agencies as “data relating to patient health status and/or the delivery of health care routinely collected from a variety of sources” (1, 2). RWD can be derived from several data sources including, but not limited to, electronic health records, medical claims data, data from product or disease registries, and data collected from other digital sources (1, 2). They are considered secondary data sources as the data are used for research questions different from the original purpose they were collected for. RWD is used for real-world evidence (RWE) generation to support drug and vaccine post-marketing studies, on safety and effectiveness, and is increasingly considered to support regulatory and payers decision (2). With strong external validity and improvements in available data quality and analytical methods, RWE are a cost-effective option for evidence generation. It contributes to accelerate product development and bring health innovation faster to all patients, including vulnerable populations traditionally excluded from randomized control trial (3). Increased and extended use of RWE is however seen mainly in countries with the capacity to generate and host robust and representative RWD sources in their public or private health ecosystem (4-6). Health regulatory institutions of China, United States, Europe and other advanced economies, through research and guidelines publications, support the increased use of RWE throughout product life cycles alongside randomized clinical trials (1, 2, 5-9).

The COVID-19 pandemic was a catalyst for the use of RWE to supplement clinical trial data and accelerate vaccine regulatory approval (7). However, it also highlighted the health inequities in global response to the pandemic, in terms of access and speed of access to COVID-19 treatment and vaccines. The main factors identified were vaccine nationalism, manufacturing and funding capacity (10). Countries' capacity to accelerate vaccine regulatory approval, including generating evidence on vaccine safety, efficacy, and effectiveness on their population, also contributed to the observed heterogeneity in national pandemic response (10-13). As COVID-19 became endemic, it remains a public health concern. Rates of vaccination are still heterogeneous globally and in highly vaccinated population, waning immunity and emergence of new variants represent ongoing challenges to long term effective control (14, 15). Continuous epidemiologic surveillance, and capacity to monitor updated vaccine effectiveness (VE) over time is key to the control of COVID-19 disease.

Southeast Asia (SEA) and India, represent >25% of the world population. It's a heterogeneous region,

constituted by countries at different level of economic development, with a majority of middle- and low-income countries. The region is particularly vulnerable to communicable diseases and other threats to human lives (16, 17). Although, major advancement were made in the last decade in most of these countries' health systems, they were impacted by the COVID-19 pandemic (18). Understanding the capacity and contribution of countries in SEA to COVID-19 vaccine effectiveness data generation is an important component of the COVID-19 disease control in the region and globally.

The aim of this study is to quantify the geographic distribution of RWE literature on COVID-19 VE with a particular focus on SEA and India, and to identify clinical sites in SEA with the capability to conduct COVID-19 VE studies, leveraging their existing databases.

Methods

This study was conducted in two steps from November 2022 to March 2023. First, a literature review and geographic analysis of the literature was conducted to identify countries of interest. Then a hospital-based cross-sectional survey was conducted in hospitals from selected countries to assess their RWE generation capability.

Literature review and publications' geographic distribution

Using the International Vaccine Access Center's (IVAC) VE studies repository, the geographic distribution of VE studies per World Health Organization (WHO) region was calculated (19). The search strategy and eligibility criteria of publications included in the IVAC repository have been published elsewhere and are publicly available from IVAC's platform (20). The list of COVID-19 VE studies were extracted from the IVAC web platform VIEW-hub on 19 January 2023 (21). The publication records were classified using the 6 WHO regions: Africa (AFRO), Americas, Eastern Mediterranean, Europe (EURO), SEA and Western Pacific (WP). Publications including multiple countries were put in a separate multi-country category. Original publications, i.e. excluding reports collating several studies and duplicate publication, in English were further categorized based on their RWD status. Publications using existing databases, such as electronic medical record (EMR), registry, surveillance databases, to generate VE were categorized as RWD. Publications collecting data, using patient interview/survey or chart review, for all or part of the variables used for the VE assessment were categorized as non-RWD. Publications including several sites combining sites with RWD and

site with non-RWD data sources were categorized as mixed-RWD. Type of data source (RWD, non-RWD and mixed-RWD) were assessed by two authors. Publications for which the data source was unclear (i.e. not clearly stated or identifiable from publication title, abstract or main text or full text not available) and the two authors disagreed were reviewed by a third author. The third author decision (RWD, non-RWD, mixed or unclear) was kept as final decision of the publication status. The proportion of studies using RWD source for each country was calculated.

Selection of countries and clinical sites survey

A convenience sample of sites in SEA from IQVIA's SEA clinical research network were selected. Sites were included if they had specialty service in infectious diseases and/or vaccine and/or multispecialty, available contact details, recent or regular contact with IQVIA clinical team, and no history of a COVID-19 database feasibility assessment conducted by IQVIA.

Survey development and administration

Survey questions were developed based on the vACCine COVID-19 monitoring readinESS (ACCESS) protocol (22) and using database feasibility assessment questionnaire templates tested in past site feasibilities conducted by the authors. The survey covered four domains: 1) site characteristics, including availability of electronic medical records, and interest in research, 2) patient demographic and clinical data, 3) operational process for data access, and 4) site experience and interest in conducting vaccine safety or effectiveness study and in secondary database research. The four domains were divided in two sections: site screening (domain 1) and capability assessment (domains 2, 3 and 4). The site screening section focused on a set of minimum criteria for conducting COVID-19 VE studies: admission of COVID-19 patients, existence of EMR and site interest. The questionnaire end at screening sections for sites not meeting these three selection criteria. Patient demographic and clinical data were classified into two groups: "must-have" and "good-to-have" (Table 1). "Must-have" variables were key variables and covariates necessary to conduct robust COVID-19 VE analysis as per WHO guidelines. These include data specific to COVID-19 diagnosis, immunization history and health outcomes as well as known individual potential confounding factors (23). All other variables were categorized as "Good-to-have". The details of questions and data collected are available in table S1.

An online self-completion questionnaire was developed using Microsoft Office Forms (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA, USA).

The questionnaire was emailed to selected sites in February 2023 to be completed by March 2023. A reminder email was sent out in March 2023 to sites which had not yet completed the survey. A closure email was sent out end of March 2023. Additional, ad hoc communications and reminders were sent to sites that replied directly to the survey invitation email.

Statistical analysis

Geographic distribution of COVID-19 VE literature

The number of articles per region and the proportion of publications using RWD sources (e.g. EMR, registry, surveillance database, etc.) per country were calculated.

Site survey response rate

The survey response rate was reported as percentage of site that responded and completed the questionnaire among number of sites contacted. Limited information was available from sites which did not respond to the survey. For most sites number of beds was available and described.

Site capability assessment

A site capability group was developed based on the site responses to the four domains surveyed (see table S2). The capability group included poor capability, medium capability, and good capability.

Domain 1: Site characteristics and interest

Site characteristics were classified as good or poor based on availability of an EMR and interest of the site in conducting secondary database research as presented in table S2.

Domain 2: Data availability

Percentage of variables available per site in each country and number of variables available in each category ("Good-to-have"; "Must-Have") for each site were calculated.

Data availability was classified as good, fair or poor based on a combination of percentage of total variables collected and completeness of "must-have" variables (table S2). If the site reported no availability of COVID-19 immunization status (i.e. vaccine brand and vaccination dates) and/or no availability of PCR results (i.e. laboratory results and date of sampling), they were

classified as poor, regardless of other variables' availability.

Domain 3: Data access

Data access to conduct research by industry sponsor was classified into two categories, no (poor) and yes (good) (see table S2).

Domain 4: Experience

Site experience in conducting vaccine effectiveness or safety study, and/or performing secondary database analysis was ranked in 3 categories, no experience (poor), experience in conducting vaccine study or secondary database analysis (fair), and experience in both conducting vaccine study and secondary database analysis (good) as demonstrated in table S2.

Site capability distribution per country

Based on the above domain scores three site capability groups were defined (table 2):

- Good: All four domains received the highest score, with the exception of site experience, which may be considered fair.
 - Average: Good or fair for data availability, good in interest and access but poor in experience.
 - Limited: Insufficient data access or site data availability, independent of other domain scores.
- All data was analyzed using Microsoft Office Excel (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, Washington, USA).

Results

COVID-19 VE publication characteristics

As of 19th January 2023, a total of 413 COVID-19 VE publications were listed on the IVAC web platform: 6 (1%) from Africa, 182 (44%) from the Americas, 24 (6%) from Eastern Mediterranean, 165 (40%) from Europe, 8 (2%) from SEA and 21 (5%) from WP. An additional 7 (2%) publications were multi-country studies (five exclusively in European countries; two combining Europe and the Americas). African, Eastern Mediterranean, and Asian countries represented 14% of all publications, with 7% coming from countries in SEA and WP. The RWD status of a total of 406 publications were assessed, details of publications exclusion are presented in supplementary material Figure S.1. In all regions, the majority of publications were RWD, ranging from 50% in AFRO to 96% in East Med. The rates per country were heterogeneous with Egypt and Zambia being the only two countries without RWD publications. WP country

publications were driven by China, Singapore, and Malaysia, respectively 57%, 100% and 100% were RWD publications as shown in table 3.

Survey response rate

A total of 55 sites from the IQVIA SEA clinical research network were contacted in India (9 sites), Indonesia (4 sites), Malaysia (12 sites), Philippines (6 sites), Singapore (13 sites), Thailand (7 sites) and Viet Nam (4 sites). Sites selected were heterogeneous in number of beds with a minimum of 30 beds, maximum of 2,300 beds and a median at 815 beds within the 48 sites for which the information was available

Of the 55 sites contacted, 19 responded (median 750 beds, minimum 120 beds, maximum 1,600 beds within the 17 sites for which the information was available) and 8 fully completed the survey (median 775 beds, minimum 120 beds, maximum 1,600 beds). Sites from India, Malaysia, Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Viet Nam responded. However, the survey completion rate was 14.5% (7.7%-33.3% per country) and there was no completed survey from Indonesia, Thailand, or Viet Nam (Figure 1).

Sites' characteristics and capability for COVID 19 VE research

A total of eight sites fully completed the survey. All sites, with the exception of one in the Philippines, acknowledged being referral centers during the pandemic. Six of these seven sites admitted both COVID-19 and other patients, while one in India admitted only COVID-19 patients. All eight sites used ICD-10 codes to collect COVID-19 patient data as part of the hospital EMR system; however, one site did not report the diagnosis coding method. In addition, half of the sites used the EMR to collect outpatient data. Although data format was not factored into the data availability score, two sites had all of their available data in electronic structured and unstructured formats, while five sites had a mix of electronic structured/unstructured, images/scans, and paper formats. Despite establishing an EMR, one site in India indicated that all data was available in paper format.

Data availability varied between 63% and 92% across the eight sites. Age, gender, residence, comorbidities, and medication use were all "must-have variables" for all participants. Six sites lacked socioeconomic status, while two lacked healthcare worker status. The "must-have" outcome variables were accessible in all eight sites. COVID-19 immunization status and PCR test variables were "must-have" for six and seven sites, respectively. However, the coverage of this material varied amongst sites. One site did not employ PCR testing to determine status, but did use it for patients

who had a negative antigen rapid test (ART) and symptoms consistent with COVID-19. All other sites reported performing PCR testing (one site) or a mix of PCR and ART tests. COVID-19 vaccination status availability ranged from not available for any patients (two sites) to available for all admitted patients (one site), even those who had not been vaccinated on-site. All locations expressed an interest in performing COVID-19 vaccine effectiveness studies, and seven sites had access to data. One location could not perform industry-sponsored research.

The capability group included three sites with "Limited capability" in India, Malaysia and the Philippines. There were four "Average Capability" sites: two in India, one in Malaysia, and one in Singapore. There was only one "Good Capability" location in the Philippines (Table 4).

Discussion

In this study, based on data from the IVAC platform, only 7% of all COVID-19 VE studies were conducted in Asia. The proportion of publications using RWD per Asian countries varied widely, (0 to 100%), but nearly 70% (20) of these publications were RWD. This was driven by Malaysia and Singapore which had respectively seven and four COVID-19 VE studies, all using RWD. These studies were all part of government mandated COVID-19 VE monitoring initiatives using their respective national COVID-19 surveillance and immunization databases. The databases used have restricted access and a specific focus on COVID-19, therefore are not representative of the general RWD capability in both countries.

A limitation of this study is the site representativity. A small number of sites took part to the survey, and all sites surveyed are part of a clinical research network, with interest and experience in research. There was a low response rate. This may be associated with the survey primary contacts who were the clinical site team. In some settings EMR are managed by a dedicated information technology (IT) team and clinical teams have limited to no exposure to their EMR beyond clinical practice use. Some sites communicated through email that the survey was forwarded to their IT/Database analytics team or investigator for response. Targeting those key teams or individuals may have increase the response rate, however their contact details were not readily available. The low response rate obtained from a small convenient sample of sites, may not be representative of the healthcare environment of each country. Hence, these results should be interpreted with caution.

In addition, our data availability assessment scoring may have been impacted by practical considerations.

To lessen the burden on the survey respondents we didn't investigate the completeness of data of interest. The data availability domain only captured presence or absence of the data. However, factors such as completeness, or format (structured vs unstructured data), impact secondary research complexity, time, and cost. The heterogeneity of the population for which vaccination brand and date were available varied by sites (only patients vaccinated at site, only patients testing positive for COVID-19 in site or referral, for all patients suspected and tested for COVID-19) and was not reflected in our score. This impacts study population representativity, possible study design, or altogether feasibility of COVID-19 VE study.

Finally, three sites indicated feasible data linkage to their national COVID-19 immunization registry, one site scoring poor for that domain and two other sites scoring fair and good. The sites scoring poor and fair, may have a secondary database research capability under-estimated by our scoring system as data not available or incomplete within their database would be available through data linkage. In all three cases, PCR tests were used to determine patients' COVID-19 status, but in different proportions of suspected patients (10% to 100%) in combination with rapid antigen detection. WHO recommends utilizing PCR tests over rapid antigen tests to diagnose COVID-19, thus sites that use a combination of PCR and rapid antigen tests may have a PCR tested patient population not representative of their overall COVID-19 patients population (23).

However, valuable insights were captured from this survey. Among the 14 sites that admitted COVID-19 patients, 57% (8) reported having an EMR and fully completed the survey. The Philippines and Vietnam were the only SEA countries surveyed that did not have any COVID-19 VE published studies listed on the IVAC platform.

Indonesia and Thailand both had only one RWD study published. This survey identified two potential sites in the Philippines, including the only one rated as "Good Capability" in the survey. No Indonesian site responded to the survey. There were no sites from Vietnam or Thailand that qualified to complete the survey. In Thailand, two sites responded but indicated no EMR, and one site in Vietnam reported no admission of COVID-19 patients.

Although this survey was focused on the feasibility of a COVID-19 VE study, general information about the sites' team, EMR structure and operational processes were captured. Hence, the results are a useful indicator for secondary database analysis capability in the sites for other diseases or therapeutic areas.

Table 1. List of demographics, outcomes, COVID-19 test and immunization status variables assessed for availability

Must-have variables	Good-to-have variables
Demographics	
Age, Gender, Geographic residence Chronic conditions (e.g. diabetes, asthma, cancer)	Race and/or ethnicity, Socioeconomic Nursing home; or extended care facility stays Health care worker status Pregnancy Pregnancy start and end dates Body mass index Smoking status Medication use Receipt of other vaccines (e.g. influenza vaccine, childhood vaccines)
Outcomes	
Dates of hospitalizations Admission diagnosis Intensive care unit admissions Date of in-hospital death Cause of in-hospital death Dates and diagnosis of emergency department visit	Discharge diagnosis from hospitalizations Ventilator use Dates and diagnosis of outpatient specialist visit Dates and diagnosis of primary care visit Dates and result of laboratory test (outpatient care) Dates and type of procedures (outpatient care) Medicine dispensing Medicine prescriptions (outpatient care)
COVID-19 test and immunization status	
Date of COVID-19 vaccination COVID-19 vaccination brand PCR test-date of sampling PCR test-results PCR test-positive result only	PCR test-test brand Antigen rapid test-date of sampling Antigen rapid test-test brand Antigen rapid test- results Antigen rapid test-positive result only

Abbreviations: PCR, polymerase chain reaction

Table 2. Capability group based on the score of the 4 domains assessed in the survey: interest from site, data availability, possibility of access to data and experience conducting database or vaccine/safety studies

Capability Group	Interest from site		Data availability*		Access		Experience					
Good	Good		AND	Good	AND	Good	AND	Good				
	Good			Good		Good			Fair			
Average	Good		AND	Good	AND	Good	AND			Poor		
	Good			Fair		Good		AND	Good			
	Good			Fair		Good		AND	Good	Fair		
	Good			Fair		Good		AND	Good	AND		Poor
Limited	Good	Poor	OR	Poor	OR		AND	Good				
	Good	Poor		Poor		Poor			Fair			
	Good	Poor		Poor		Poor			Poor			

*Sites without immunization status and/or PCR test results scored 1 for data availability.

Table 3. Type of data source used in COVID-19 vaccine effectiveness publications from each country

Region (N, % of total)	Country	N. Publication	RWD source
AFRO (6, 1%)	South Africa	5	60%
	Zambia	1	0%
Americas (180, 44%)	Argentina	4	100%
	Brazil	15	100%
	Canada	24	96%
	Chile	6	100%
	Colombia	4	100%
	Cuba	1	100%
	Mexico	1	100%
	Paraguay	1	100%
	United States of America	124	67%
Eastern Mediterranean (23, 6%)	Egypt	1	0%
	Kuwait	1	100%
	Lebanon	1	100%
	Morocco	2	100%
	Qatar	15	100%
	Turkey	1	100%
	United Arab Emirates	2	100%
EURO (161, 40%)	Belgium	2	100%
	Czechia	4	100%
	Denmark	9	100%
	Finland	4	100%
	France	4	75%
	Germany	1	0%
	Greece	1	100%
	Hungary	2	100%
	Iceland	1	100%
	Israel	51	86%
	Italy	10	100%
	Netherlands	2	100%
	Norway	4	100%
	Portugal	3	100%
	San Marino	1	100%
	Spain	9	78%
	Sweden	6	100%
United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland	47	72%	

Multi-countries (7, 2%)	Multi-countries in European countries	5	0%
	Multi-countries combining Europe and the Americas	2	100%
SEA (8, 2%)	India	3	67%
	Indonesia	1	100%
	Republic of Korea	2	50%
	Thailand	2	50%
Western Pacific (21, 5)	Australia	1	100%
	China	7	57%
	Japan	2	50%
	Malaysia	4	100%
	Singapore	7	100%

AFRO: Africa; N: number; EURO: Europe; RWD: real-world data; SEA: Southeast Asia

Table 4. Site capability group for COVID 19 vaccine effectiveness secondary databases research

Site	Domain's score				Capability group
	Data availability	Interest from sites	Data access for research	Experience conducting database study	
IN 1	Poor*	Good	Good	Good	Limited
IN 2	Fair	Good	Good	Fair	Average
IN 3	Fair	Good	Good	Poor	Average
MY 1	Fair	Good	Good	Poor	Average
MY 2	Poor*	Good	Poor	Poor	Limited
PH 1	Good	Good	Good	Fair	Good
PH 2	Poor*	Good	Good	Poor	Limited
SG	Fair	Good	Good	Good	Average

*Hospitals without immunization status and/or PCR test results scored 1 for data availability. Abbreviations: MY, Malaysia; IN, India; PCR, polymerase chain reaction; PH, Philippines; SG, Singapore

EMR = Electronic Medical Record; VE = Vaccine Effectiveness

Figure 1. Flow chart of sites surveyed

COVID-19 pandemic response has benefitted globally from exceptional level of national investment and resources allocated to surveillance and control, allowing active detection of cases, and creation of platforms to collect data on diagnosis, immunization, and health outcomes (26). It has resulted in unprecedented speed in terms of epidemiological understanding of the disease and development and evaluation of therapeutic drugs and vaccines. To support ongoing COVID-19 disease control, it remains important to ensure continuous monitoring of the disease epidemiology, overall burden, effectiveness and safety of therapeutics and vaccines. This survey investigates the secondary database analysis capability in sites located in an economically diverse group of countries in SEA. It contributes to support reducing the health inequity gap associated with the representation of low and middle income countries in research (27). Finally, with WHO vaccines fast approval track and emergency use authorization, identifying sites where vaccine effectiveness studies can be efficiently designed and approved following launch of vaccine in low- and middle-income countries will improve vaccine access.

Conclusion

This survey demonstrates the potential for secondary database analysis for COVID-19 RWE VE studies in countries in SEA where limited RWE were published at time of the analysis. It is a useful tool to identify sites in which a robust feasibility assessment can be conducted to collect additional insights, essential to design and execute any secondary database study.

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Authors' contribution

AFT contributed to the conception and design, analysis and interpretation of data; drafted the article and revised it critically for important intellectual content; provided final approval of the version to be published and agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

SHC contributed to the analysis and interpretation of data; drafted the article and revised it critically for important intellectual content; provided final approval of the version to be published and agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

FCY contributed to the conception of the study and interpretation of data; revised it critically for important

intellectual content; provided final approval of the version to be published and agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

NJK contributed to the conception of the study and interpretation of data; revised it critically for important intellectual content; provided final approval of the version to be published and agreement to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Conflict of interest

AFT, SHC, YCF and NJK are employees of IQVIA, a Contract Research Organization engaged by pharmaceutical companies that market products for the prevention or treatment of COVID-19 infection. AFT has ownership of shares in companies that market products for the prevention or treatment of COVID-19 infection.

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Appendix

Table S1. Category and list of questions of the COVID-19 secondary research capability survey

	N	Question	Answer
Database description			
COVID-19 admission	1	Were you a COVID-19 referral center during the pandemic?	1. Yes, please specify the period of time 2. No
	2	Were you admitting only COVID-19 patients?	1. COVID-19 only 2. COVID-19 and other patients
	3	Do you currently admit COVID-19 patients?	1. Yes 2. No
Site description	4	Number of bed available in your hospital:	[numeric]
	5	What is the geographic area covered by your hospital database	[free text]
	6	Does your hospital have an electronic medical record system that captures admission and discharge information (diagnoses, treatment and procedures)?	1. Yes 2. No
	6b	Does COVID-19 patients data recorded in your hospital database or a dedicated database?	1. In hospital database with all admitted patients 2. In a dedicated COVID-19 database
	7	How are hospital admissions coded?	1. ICD-9 2. ICD-10 3. Other, specify: [free text]
	8	Do you also capture codes for outpatient hospital visits?	1. Yes 2. No
	9	Interest to participate in COVID-19 vaccine effectiveness studies on hospital data	1. Yes 2. No, specify why: [free text]

Data availability			
Patient Characteristics	10	Please indicate if the following information about is available in your data source?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Age 2.Gender 3.Race and/or Ethnicity, 4.Geographic residence of patients, 5.Socioeconomic information, 6.Health care worker status, chronic conditions (e.g. diabetes, asthma, cancer), 7.Nursing home; or extended care facility stays, 8.Pregnancy 9.Pregnancy start and end dates 10.Body mass index, 11.Smoking status; 12.Medication use, 13.Receipt of other vaccines (e.g. influenza vaccine, childhood vaccines)
Patient Outcome	11	Please indicate if the following information about is available in your data source?	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Dates of hospitalizations, 2.Admission diagnosis, 3.Discharge diagnosis from hospitalizations, 4.Intensive care unit admissions, 5.Ventilator use, 6.Date of in-hospital death, 7.Cause of in-hospital death, 8.dates and diagnosis of emergency department visit, 9.Dates and diagnosis of outpatient specialist visit, 10.Dates and diagnosis of primary care visit, 11.Dates and result of laboratory test (outpatient care), 12.Dates and type of procedures (outpatient care), 13.medicine dispensing, 14.Medicine prescriptions (outpatient care),

	11b	Please indicate if your database can be linked to death registries	1. Yes, specify process and timelines: [free text] 2. No
Patients COVID-19 status	12	How do you assess COVID-19 status in your hospital? For all option please indicate if the information is available in your database	1. PCR (data available in electronic format for: a) date of sampling, b)test brand, c) results, d) only positive results) 2. Antigen Rapid Test ((data available in electronic format for: a) date of sampling, b)test brand, c) results, d) only positive results) 3. Other, specify: [free text]
	12b	Please indicate if your database can be linked to your hospital laboratory?	1. Yes, (Does the lab conduct additional respiratory disease test (e.g. Influenza, RSV, etc), specify: [free text] 2. No
Patient COVID-19 Vaccine	13	Does your database contains the exact date of vaccination and brand for each COVID-19 vaccine dose for the following admitted patients:	1. All patients admitted 2. Patients admitted for suspicion of COVID-19 and tested for COVID-19 3. Patients testing positive for COVID-19 4. COVID-19 positive patients referred from other hospital 5. Patients vaccinated in site 6. No detailed COVID-19 vaccination data 7. Other, specify: [free text]
	13 b	Please indicate if your database can be linked to your local/national COVID-19 vaccine registry?	1. Yes, specify process and timelines: [free text] 2. No
Operational			
	14	Can you conduct research sponsored by industry in your database	1. Yes 2. No
	15	Would informed consent be needed for you to extract and use data from your hospital for research?	1. Yes 2. No
	16	Please describe any necessary ethics and/or institutional approvals that your organization would need to obtain to participate in this study, including timelines:	[free text]

Experience			
	17	Has your organization participated in other vaccine safety or effectiveness studies? Please provide PMIDs of published studies (up to 5).	1. Yes 2. No
	18	Do you have experience in conducting multi-database studies using a common data model and common analytics?	1. Yes 2. No
	19	Would you be able to run a R-script to analyze the data and share aggregated results?	1. Yes 2. No
	20	Would you be able to share pseudonymized data outside of your country, compliant with GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation)?	1. Yes 2. No
	21	Would you be able to extract the study specific data and transform them locally into a pre-defined data model (CSV files)?	1. Yes 2. No
	22	Would you like to share any other thoughts or comments on the capability of your organization to participate in this study?	[free text]

Table S2. Evaluation matrix and score for the 4 domains assess in the survey: interest from site, data availability, possibility of access to data and experience conducting database or vaccine/safety studies

Score	Interest from site	Data availability	Access	Experience
Good	Yes	With >80% and captured all must-have variables	Yes	Yes, with experience
Fair	-	With 50-80% and captured all/some must-have variables	-	Some experience
Poor	No	With <50% and/or captured some/no must-have variables	No	No experience

Figure S1. Flow chart of literature review and geographical categorization